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Perceived Impact Of Quality Assurance Management Processes On Students' Academic Performance In Public Tertiary Institutions, Taraba State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined perceived impact of quality assurance management processes on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba state Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level, descriptive survey research design was adopted. One thousand nine hundred and eleven (1,911) academic staff for the 2024/2025 academic Session, the sample size for the study is 397 determined using Taro Yamane formulas. The instrument for data collection is a self-developed structured questionnaire, titled 'Quality assurance and students' academic performance questionnaire (QASAPQ). The QASAPQ was validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education. The reliability of QASAPQ was established using Cronbach-alpha method which yielded a reliability index of 0.751 index. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic of chi-square. The mean was used to answer the research questions while the chi-square statistics was used to test the Null hypotheses. The findings from the study revealed that staff training and development, and accreditation are all impactful on students' academic performance in State tertiary institutions, Taraba state Nigeria. it was concluded that that quality assurance management processes significantly impact students' academic performance in state public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. Based on the findings from this study, it is therefore, recommended among others that: public tertiary institutions in Taraba State should implement regular and structured training and professional development programs tailored to address current educational challenges, emerging trends, and specific institutional needs. This will enhance staff competencies and positively influence students' academic performance.

Keywords: Quality assurance, Quality assurance management processes, Students' academic performance, tertiary institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance of students serves as the cornerstone of the education system, determining the effectiveness and success of educational institutions. It is a critical measure used to evaluate whether an institution is achieving its goals and meeting the expectations of various stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and policymakers. Parents, in particular, hold high expectations for students' academic performance, associating it with better career opportunities, financial security, and future stability. These

expectations drive significant investments in education and motivate efforts to improve learning outcomes. Narad and Abdullah (2016) described academic performance as the knowledge acquired by students, typically measured through marks or grades assigned by teachers. This definition highlights the role of academic assessments as a key indicator of students' understanding and mastery of subjects. In an educational context, academic performance represents the attainment of specific goals set for students, teachers, or institutions over a given period. It is measured through a variety of methods, including formal examinations, continuous assessments, and practical evaluations. In essence, students' academic performance reflects the extent to which educational objectives have been met.

The academic performance of students is influenced by a complex interplay of factors. These include personal attributes such as personality traits, intellectual abilities, and motivation, which shape students' capacity to learn and excel. Additionally, the school environment and climate play a pivotal role. A positive and supportive environment fosters engagement, reduces distractions, and encourages better performance. For instance, schools that provide modern facilities, maintain effective leadership, and support innovative teaching practices are better equipped to improve student outcomes (Adetayo & Adewale, 2020). Therefore, students' academic performance could be achieved through quality assurance practices or practice employed by tertiary institutional administration. Quality assurance process or practice is seen as the all planned and systematic actions or process necessary for providing sufficient confidence to school managers and students or products or and services being offered will satisfy the required quality used. It is a process of ensuring that controlled mechanisms to maintain and enhance standard or quality of work done (Edumark, 2016). Quality assurance is a systematic process of ensuring that all activities necessary to design, develop, and implement a product or service are effective and efficient with respect to the system and its performance (Juran, 2019). The term systematic process indicates a structured and organized approach to ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of all activities involved in designing, developing, and implementing a product or service. This definition underscores the importance of a comprehensive and methodical system that considers the entire lifecycle of a product or service, promoting reliability and consistency in outcomes.

In the school system, quality assurance is the totality of the system's resources and information devoted to setting up, maintaining and improving the quality and standard of teaching, mentoring and monitoring, research and services to the public. Mensah (2019) described quality assurance to involves the evaluation of a system or a school and its operations against certain prescribed standards or quality for self-assurance and to ensure that control devices are working to make output or result correspond to set objectives. In the context of teaching and learning, quality assurance means the process of ensuring that practices and procedures or actions to enhance quality and excellence in the key areas of delivery and test administration are complied with. quality assurance all the efforts being made by government, non-educational agencies, education planners and school authorities to provide quality education to students. It is the provision of tools that can be used to establish confidence that activities which centre on knowledge articulation and transformation of students are carried out with optimum standards in school. It therefore speaks of the provisions and effectiveness of methods that ensure quality teaching and mentorship in school (Edumark, 2016). Quality assurance in education involves a set of systematic and continuous actions that institutions, staff and policymakers take to ensure that students' academic programmes meet predefined standards and objectives, fostering an environment of effective teaching and learning (Smith, 2017).

Quality assurance management processes encompass the systematic activities and methods employed to ensure that products or services meet specified standards and fulfil customer expectations throughout the entire production or service delivery lifecycle (Ibu, 2018). Quality assurance management processes are the planned and systematic activities implemented to ensure that processes and systems consistently produce outcomes that meet predetermined quality criteria (American Society for Quality, 2020). The quality assurance management processes as used in this study to enhance students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State include staff training and development and accreditation.

These mechanisms are instrumental in fostering academic staff development, ensuring compliance with standards, and promoting accountability (Nwankwo & Eze, 2017).

Staff training and development is another quality assurance management process in which the institutions provide to their staff to update their knowledge to enhance students' academic performance. Training and development refer to the formal efforts that are made within organizations to improve the performance and commitment of their employees through a variety of educational methods and programmes (Shodinde, 2015). It includes various tools, instructions, and activities designed to improve employee performance. It's an opportunity for staff to increase their knowledge and upgrade their skills. The concepts of training and development are used interchangeably. However, it can be differentiated from the other. Training is for specific job purpose while development goes beyond specifics. Development covers not only those activities which improve staff' performance, but also those brings about growth of personality. Training is a formal process by which talented development professionals help individuals to improve their performance at work organization, while Development in the other hand, is the acquisition of knowledge, skill, or attitude and so on, to prepare staff for new tasks or responsibilities that might be assigned to them. By implication, training appears to be the corner-stone of sound or effective and productive performance in work place towards the realization of quality work. Training is also seemed to be actively and intimately connected with all the personnel and managerial functions. It may be difficult for educational managers or administrators to excel on quality assurance Management without adequate training and development programmes. Training is a practical and vital necessity for Managers and administrators to enhance staff performance in work place. Training serves as quality assurance management process to facilitate staff performance in work organization. Hussein (2016) explained that the most popular training and development methods used by organizations can be classified as either on the job or off the job training. On-the-job training or internal training: This is the process where people are trained at their workplace. It's easy and cost-efficient for the organization to organize. On the job training, the organization has significant control over what is being taught and the method include job rotation, coaching, apprenticeships, temporary promotions, and so on.

Off-the-job training or external training: In this process of training, the organization uses external resources such as people and other resource materials. to train its workforce. It has the advantage of being held by professionals and doesn't impact the school's regular operations. This training may also take the form of computer-based training, which offers the advantage of conducting it anywhere in the world. This training method can include lectures, seminars, conferences, business simulations and so on. A well-trained staff would make a better and economic use of materials and equipment which would go a long way to minimize wastages and uplift the quality standard of an institution.

Accreditation is the formal evaluation of institutions and their programs against established quality standards, typically involving assessments of faculty qualifications, infrastructure, curriculum, and governance (Ezeokoli & Okafor, 2020). The accreditation process motivates institutions to meet high-quality benchmarks, enhancing institutional credibility and ensuring that programs produce competent graduates. Accreditation directly influences students' academic performance by fostering environments that support effective learning and research (Okoro et al., 2020). In Taraba State, accreditation processes are often delayed or incomplete due to limited funding and inadequate preparation. Many programs fail to meet accreditation standards, which adversely affects institutional credibility and student confidence. The lack of fully accredited programs limits students' exposure to high-quality education, thereby impacting their academic performance and future employability (Nwachukwu et al., 2023). The role of quality assurance management processes in enhancing students' academic performance is crucial. Prioritizing staff training and development, and ensuring timely and thorough accreditation are essential strategies for addressing existing gaps. By overcoming these challenges, state tertiary institutions in Taraba State can create an environment conducive to academic excellence and equip students with the skills needed to thrive in a competitive world.

Nur et al. (2022) investigated the impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance. The findings indicate that all three hypotheses are accepted, as having significant impact on

organizational performance. This indicated that training and development have significant impact on organizational performance. Similarly, Nechirwan et al. (2021) investigated the Role of Training and Development on Organizational Effectiveness at small and medium enterprises in Kurdistan region of Iraq. The study revealed that there a direct impact of development programs on the organizational effectiveness and its progress and development is essential for an effective organization. In same vein, Obiekwe & Obiekwe (2021) explored the relationship between teachers' training and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' training and students' success in external examinations, learning abilities, and participation in extracurricular activities.

Okafor (2022) conducted a descriptive survey study titled "Perceived Impact of Accreditation on Students' Academic Performance in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. Findings indicated that accreditation processes were perceived to have a significant positive impact on teaching quality, curriculum relevance, and ultimately on students' academic performance. Similarly, Obadara and Alaka (2013) carried out a study on Accreditation and Quality Assurance in Nigerian. The findings revealed that there is significant relationship between accreditation and resource input into Nigerian universities, quality of output, quality of process, and no significant relationship between accreditation and quality of academic content. Additionally, Appolus and Nkechi (2021) carried out a study on Impact Assessment of Accreditation on Quality in Higher Education in Nigeria: The Study of North-East Geo Political Zone. Results of the finding revealed that accreditation has significant impact on quality in Higher Education in Nigeria, it also reveals that some universities resort to falsehood, borrowing of staff and equipment from other schools, to attract high score during accreditation which are not sustained; it reveals that facilities and library holdings improved tremendously through accreditation visits.

Statement of the Problem

Students' academic performance is a centre which the whole education system revolves around. However, the researcher observed that students seemed to performed bellow expectation. They appear to be involved in examination malpractice, cultism, some graduates couldn't write effectively, speak fluently or construct a good sentence, their performance is below the expected standard where by the outputs does not match the societal expectations and employment needs. Despite the invaluable roles of quality assurance management processes on students' academic performance, it was also observed that Students' poor academic performance seemed to have been attributed to inadequate quality assurance management processes such as staff training and development and accreditation the researchers also observes that these institutions seem to be falling short in maintaining the required level of quality that guarantees standard and quality education. Students' poor performance also attributed to staff' incompetency such as in the use of methods of teaching, poor mastery of subject matter, unclear expression, inadequate use of instructional materials, lack of skill such as; human relation skill, supervisory skill, communication skill, ICT skill, technical skill, analytical skill to harness or plan, coordinate, control the students for good academic performance, poor students' academic performance appears also to be laxity of school climate or administration.

Despite the effort of the regulatory bodies such as the National Universities Commission (NUC) and the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and Taraba State government and its agencies to enhance the quality of education through improved infrastructure and funding to ensure that public tertiary institutions within the state receive ample resources to guarantee the quality of education provided to learners, ensure quality assurance management so as to enhance students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, yet the issues of poor academic performance persisted. Some stakeholders attributed the poor students' academic performance due to staff' incompetency to harness or plan, coordinate and control to promote students' academic performance. It is against this background that the researcher carried out the study on perceived impact of quality assurance management processes on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the perceived impact of quality assurance management processes on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba state Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine perceived impact of:

1. staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted. One thousand nine hundred and eleven (1,911) academic staff for the 2024/2025 academic Session, the sample size for the study is 397 determined using Taro Yamane formulas. The instrument for data collection is a self-developed structured questionnaire, titled 'Quality assurance and students' academic performance questionnaire (QASAPQ). The QASAPQ was validated by three experts from the faculty of education. The reliability of QASAPQ was established using Cronbach-alpha method which yielded a reliability index of 0.751, Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic of chi-square. The mean score of 2.50 scores was used as a criterion mean score for decision making on each item. The mean score of 2.50 and above was accepted and below 2.50 was rejected as not having desired impact; while the chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question One: *What is the impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations of Rating Scale on the impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria

Statement	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1. Workshops and seminars attended by staff have contributed to improved student learning outcomes.	3.48	0.82	A
2. Mentorship programs for academic staff have enhanced students' academic performance through better guidance	3.14	1.06	A
3. Participation in online and virtual courses has equipped staff with skills that positively impact students' results	2.99	1.09	A
4. Pedagogical training received by staff has led to more effective teaching methods that improve student understanding	3.19	1.03	A
5. Training in assessment and evaluation techniques has improved the accuracy of student performance measurement	3.10	1.02	A

6. Continuous staff development helps in adopting innovative teaching strategies that boost students' academic achievement	3.31	0.90	A
7. Staff training and development have increased students' motivation and engagement in the learning process	3.24	1.00	A
Cluster Mean/Standard deviation	3.21	0.99	A

Source: Field work (2025). Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50$ = Agreed; $X \leq 2.50$ => Disagreed

Results in table 4.1 show response on the on the Impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. All the items have the mean rating scales in the region of 2.5 to 3.48 which shows that there is Impact of staff training and development on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.21; this implies that staff training and development is impactful on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria

Research Question one: *What is the impact of accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviations of Rating Scale on the impact of accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Statement	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1. Institutional accreditation ensures that academic standards are maintained, positively impacting students' performance	3.12	0.97	A
2. Program-specific accreditation improves curriculum quality, which enhances students' academic achievements	3.10	1.06	A
3. Compliance with accreditation requirements motivates faculty to deliver higher quality instruction benefiting students	3.24	1.00	A
4. Accreditation processes lead to better infrastructure and learning resources that support student success	3.28	0.88	A
5. Regular accreditation reviews encourage continuous improvement in teaching and assessment methods, improving outcomes	3.07	1.07	A
6. Accreditation increases students' confidence in their education, positively affecting their academic motivation	3.14	0.97	A
7. Accreditation standards promote effective monitoring and evaluation practices that enhance student academic performance	3.32	0.86	A
Cluster Mean/Standard deviation	3.18	0.97	A

Source: Field work (2025). Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50$ => Agreed; $X \leq 2.50$ => Disagreed

Results in table 4.3 show responses on the impact of accreditation on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria. All the items have the mean rating scales in the region of 2.5 to 3.2 which shows that there is positive Impact of accreditation on academic staff Job performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The cluster has a mean of 3.18 this implies that accreditation improved students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria

Null Hypothesis one

There is no significant impact of staff training and development on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-square Test of impact of staff training and development on students’ academic performance in State public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	82.899	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	76.203	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	70.717	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	397		

From Table 4.6, chi-square at 20 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2 = 82.899, p = .000$). This signifies that there is significant impact of staff training and development on students’ academic performance in State public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of staff training and development on students’ academic performance in State public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria is not retained. Rejecting the hypothesis implies that there is significant impact of staff training and development on students’ academic performance in State public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Null Hypothesis two

There is no significant impact of accreditation on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of impact of accreditation on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	98.255	21	.000
Likelihood Ratio	93.263	21	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	95.010	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	397		

Table 4.8 presents chi-square test at 21 degree of freedom ($\chi^2 = 98.255, p = .000$). This signifies that there is significant impact of accreditation on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of accreditation on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria is not retained. Rejecting the hypothesis implies that there is significant impact of accreditation on students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

1. The finding of the research question one and hypothesis one shown that staff training is impactful on academic staff Job performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. The finding of the research question two and hypothesis two revealed that accreditation significantly impact on academic staff Job performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Mean and standard deviation and chi-square (χ^2) were used to answer the research question two and to test hypothesis two respectively. The analysis of the mean and standard deviation scores indicates that staff training and development significantly impact students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The mean scores for all items range from 2.99 to 3.48, highlighting the positive impact of training and development programs. The overall cluster mean is 3.21, suggesting that staff training and development contribute meaningfully to organizational development and students’

academic success. Furthermore, the chi-square analysis with 20 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2 = 82.899$, $p = .000$) confirms a statistically significant relationship between staff training and development and students' academic performance. These findings underline the importance of investing in staff development initiatives as a strategy to enhance the academic outcomes of students in public tertiary institutions.

The findings of this study align with Nur et al. (2022) whose findings indicated that all three hypotheses are accepted, as having significant impact on organizational performance. This indicated that training and development have significant impact on organizational performance. Similarly, Nechirwan et al. (2021) whose study revealed that there a direct impact of development programs on the organizational effectiveness and its progress and development is essential for an effective organization. This study is also in consonant with Obiekwe & Obiekwe (2021) whose findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' training and students' success in external examinations, learning abilities, and participation in extracurricular activities.

These studies highlight the positive impact of training programs on key performance metrics, such as job effectiveness, pedagogical skills, and students' academic success, reinforcing the conclusions drawn in this research. By addressing staff needs through well-structured training programs, institutions can significantly enhance the quality of education and contribute to students' academic success.

Mean and standard deviation and chi-square (χ^2) were used to answer the research question two and to test hypothesis two respectively. The findings of this study revealed that accreditation has a significant and positive impact on students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria. Accreditation serves as a quality assurance mechanism, ensuring that institutions meet and maintain predefined standards in educational delivery. The mean and standard deviation scores (3.10 to 3.32) indicate that accreditation is perceived as highly impactful in improving students' academic outcomes. The tested hypothesis ($\chi^2 = 98.255$, $p = .000$) further underscores the significant role of accreditation in fostering educational excellence and accountability.

The finding of this study congruence with the view of Udoh and Ogujawa (2015), who noted challenges such as temporary enhancements made by institutions during accreditation visits. Similarly, this finding agreed with Okafor (2022) findings which indicated that accreditation processes were perceived to have a significant positive impact on teaching quality, curriculum relevance, and ultimately on students' academic performance. The finding of this study is also in consonant with Appolus and Nkechi (2021) finding which revealed that accreditation has significant impact on quality in Higher Education in Nigeria, it also revealed that some universities resort to falsehood, borrowing of staff and equipment from other schools, to attract high score during accreditation which are not sustained; it reveals that facilities and library holdings improved tremendously through accreditation visits. This study aligns with established research in affirming the vital role of accreditation in enhancing students' academic performance by ensuring adherence to quality standards. However, addressing systemic challenges within accreditation processes is essential to sustain its long-term impact and credibility.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it has been concluded that quality assurance management processes significantly impact students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions, Taraba State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from this study, it was recommended that:

1. State tertiary institutions in Taraba State should implement regular and structured training and professional development programs tailored to address current educational challenges, emerging trends, and specific institutional needs. This will enhance staff competencies and positively influence students' academic performance.
2. Public tertiary institutions in Taraba State should prioritize meeting accreditation requirements by ensuring adequate resources, qualified staff, and effective teaching facilities. Regular self-

assessments and adherence to accreditation standards will boost institutional credibility and enhance students' academic success.

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